

Model characteristics of special physical preparedness of Juvenile category athletes in acrobatic rock'n'roll

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Purpose: develop model characteristics of special physical readiness of Juvenile category athletes in acrobatic rock'n'roll.

Material & Methods: theoretical analysis and synthesis of data of special scientific and methodical literature, pedagogical observation, pedagogical testing, pedagogical experiment, methods of mathematical statistics. The study involved 40 athletes (20 sports pairs of the category Juvenile).

Results: model characteristics and evaluation standards of the level of special physical readiness of athletes of the Juvenile category from acrobatic rock'n'roll are determined.

Conclusion: a system for assessing the level of special physical readiness of athletes can be used to optimize the training process in acrobatic rock'n'roll.

Keyword: acrobatic rock'n'roll, special physical readiness, model characteristics.

Introduction

Conducting research in various sports is closely related to the study of the model characteristics of the strongest athletes.

The need to use the model characteristics of the strongest athletes in the selection and orientation process is emphasized by O. A. Shinkaruk [10] in his works, and notes that the development of model characteristics of competitive activities of various parties in the athletes' preparedness allows them to be properly trained with due regard to the propensity to work with a specific orientation. create conditions for successful training and performances in competitions so that athletes can reach the planned parameters P. N. Kizim [3] developed model characteristics and evaluation standards for the level of special physical fitness of highly qualified athletes in acrobatic rock'n'roll. At present, we have not found any publications on the construction of model characteristics of special physical preparedness of athletes of the Juvenile category in acrobatic rock'n'roll. The actual problem of this sport is the lack of a scientifically based method of training athletes of the Juvenile category from acrobatic rock'n'roll, as well as the lack of methods for assessing the level of special physical preparedness of the rock ruling in this category from the training sections.

Purpose of the study: to develop the model characteristics of the special physical fitness of athletes of the category Juvenile in acrobatic rock'n'roll.

Material and Methods of the research

With the aim of a comprehensive study of the level of special physical preparedness of athletes of the studied group in the Juvenals category from acrobatic rock'n'roll, a set of tests was used to assess the athletes' preparedness in acrobatic rock and roll [5]. This complex answered a more complete and comprehensive assessment of the level of special physical preparedness in accordance with the requirements of acrobatic rock'n'roll. In the process of research, tests T1, T2, T5

were used to determine the level of development of speed-strength components; test T6 was used to determine the level of development of the power components; to determine the level of development of special endurance, we used tests: T3, T4, T7 [5].

Results of the research

The results of testing the special physical preparedness of athletes of the Juvenile category in acrobatic rock'n'roll are presented in Figures 1 and 2.

Figure 1. Results of individual testing of special physical preparedness of Juvenile category athletes in acrobatic rock'n'roll

The results of **T1** "2 somersaults forward, 1 somersault back," tour "for 30 s (number of times)", as an indicator of speed-strength training, for partners averaged 4,71 times for the group 39 times), with partners – on average 4,67 times for a group (the range of indicators was $\pm 0,49$ times);

The average **T2** indicator "Performing the main course in 20 s (number of times)", as an indicator of speed-strength training, for partners made up for the group 10,74 times (the range of indicators was $\pm 0,11$ times), for partners it averaged for a group of 11,42 times (the range of indicators was $\pm 0,21$ times).

Figure 2. Results of the general (joint) performance of the tests in a sport couple of special physical preparedness of Juvenal category in acrobatic rock'n'roll

The **T3** indicator "Lower change with a partner's turn by 540° (number of times)", as an indicator of special endurance, averaged 5,3 times for a group (the range of indicators was $\pm 0,66$ times).

The **T4** test "Upper change with the partner's turn by 720° in American spin (number of times)", as an indicator of special endurance, showed average results for the group – 4,2 times (the range of indicators was $\pm 0,62$ times);

Indicator **T5** "Lower, upper change, tour anler (in air) by 360° (number of times)", as an indicator of speed-strength training, averaged 4,5 times for a group (variation of indicators was $\pm 0,51$ times);

Test **T6** "Lower, upper change, partner's leap upward based on the partner's arms, (number of times)", as an indicator of strength training – on average, 6,5 times for a group (the range of indicators was $\pm 0,51$ times);

Test 7 "Performing a non-stop competitive program (number of times)", as an indicator of special endurance, averaged 1,4

times for a group (the range of indicators was $\pm 0,11$ times).

As a result of processing the obtained test data, we determined the model characteristics and assessment standards for the level of special physical fitness of the Juvenile category athletes from acrobatic rock'n'roll (Table 1).

The results are shown at the level of average values, we evaluate as "good", by the magnitude of the standard deviation for the better as "excellent", to the worse by the same value – "satisfactory"

Conclusions / Discussion

This study complements the theoretical foundations of building sports training in acrobatic rock'n'roll, as described in the works of the authors [1; 2; 4; 5; 10]. At the same time, in our study, for the first time, model characteristics and assessment standards of the level of special physical preparedness of athletes of the Juvenile category were determined by acrobatic rock'n'roll. The development of model characteristics and assessment standards for the level of special physical fitness of athletes of the Juvenile category in acrobatic rock'n'roll fully confirms our vision of solving the problem of improving the special physical preparedness of athletes in the Juvenile category in acrobatic rock'n'roll.

This research has developed a practical system for assessing the level of special physical preparedness for the athletes in the Juvenile category for acrobatic rock'n'roll. The model characteristics and assessment norms of the level of special physical preparedness of the athletes of the category Juvenile on acrobatic rock'n'roll are determined.

Separate characteristics and a system for assessing the level of special physical preparedness can be used to control the course of the training process.

Prospects for further research should be in the search for ways to solve the problem of improving the training process of athletes of the Juvenile category in acrobatic rock'n'roll.

Table 1
Model characteristics of the level of special physical preparedness of athletes of the Juvenile category in acrobatic rock'n'roll

Test	Test SPP	Athletes	Assessment		
			excellent	good	satisfactory
T 1	2 somersaults forward, 1 somersault back," tour "for 30 s (number of times)	male partner	5	4	3
T 1	2 somersaults forward, 1 somersault back," tour "for 30 s (number of times)	female partner	5	4	3
T 2	Perfoming the main course in 20 s (number of times)	male partners, female partners	12	11	10
T 3	Lower change with a partner's turn by 540° (number of times)	in couple	6	5	4
T 4	Upper change with the partner's turn by 720° in American spin (number of times)	in couple	5	4	3
T 5	Lower, upper change, tour anler (in air) by 360° (number of times)	in couple	5	4	3
T 6	Lower, upper change, partner's leap upward based on the partner's arms, (number of times)	in couple	7	6	5
T 7	Performing a non-stop competitive program (number of times)	in couple	1,5	1,4	1,3

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